

Lighten the Load – Reducing the carbon footprint of safety boots

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1. Introduction

Safety boots are everywhere. They are the quintessential personal protective equipment (PPE) across industries from construction to (petro)chemicals, worn daily by millions of people. The strict protective property requirements and the need for comfort for the wearer limit the range of materials that can be used. So far, the safety boots' environmental performance has been largely ignored in the design and manufacturing phase. This study is part of an Innovation Project in collaboration with a Norwegian workwear manufacturing company, ensuring access to real company data. The study quantifies the environmental performance of the current boot, identifies hotspots, and investigates possible improvements. This led to the inclusion of environmental considerations in the early design stages, creating a better-performing boot.

2. Method

First, we establish a baseline cradle-to-grave LCA for a representative safety boot and then compare it to alternative boot designs that deploy circular strategies. Replacement with alternative or bio-based textile materials, and lifetime extension are explored. The functional unit is one pair of safety boots that meets the safety standards which specify the design, construction, and classification of safety footwear (ISO, 2011) to protect the users against extrinsic factors. The reference boot is worn on average 6 months in harsh conditions (e.g. offshore petroleum industry) before it is discarded. We assume all discarded boots end up in the municipal waste stream and are sent for incineration. The reference and alternative safety boots and the LCI were developed with the manufacturer, supplemented by supplier interviews and literature data. The focus is on Global Warming Potential (GWP100) and the Ecoinvent 3.2 database in SimaPro version 9.3.0. was used for the LCA. Production is mainly in Italy and some take place in Romania, hence the respective energy mixes are used. Natural gas is also used for production in Italy and Romania. Raw materials are mostly from European suppliers and a few from Asia.

3. Results and Discussion

The results show that the carbon footprint of the reference boot is 35 kgCO₂e and that leather-based components contribute over 60% of these emissions. Figure 1a shows that 80% of the baseline emissions are from raw materials, especially for the boot's upper. Although the direct energy from production/assembly contributes about 8%, there is room for emission reduction. One possible option is a switch to renewable energy sources like solar or wind energy and replacing natural gas with biogas. Another option may be improving the energy efficiency of the production process. Using alternative materials reduces baseline emissions by 50% and switching to bio-based plastic materials compared to traditional plastics does not significantly affect the GWP results. Alternative designs facilitating lifetime extension could yield a 10-month use time extension, contributing to another 31% emissions reduction. Figure 1b shows that after switching to new carbon-efficient materials, the overall environmental burdens are less and the share of pre-processing and direct energy emissions seems higher. However, if energy emissions are addressed, the real impacts from materials can be seen. In addition to the environmental considerations, the weight of the boot was reduced from about 1.5kg per pair to around 850g per pair by reducing the number of materials used. This weight reduction has a direct impact on user comfort and consequently on work output.

The robust company data improves our confidence in the baseline results, while the results of alternative scenarios could have been strengthened if supplier data was readily available. However, the results are valid within the assumptions used. The authors also note that GWP may not be the best indicator to highlight the

impacts of switching from leather to bio-based textiles but this was outside the scope of this study and is recommended for future work. Some other indicators like land use and land use change (LULUC), water use, and toxicity could be used in addition, to provide a broader range of trade-offs. Additionally, since the alternative material market, especially bio-based materials is not fully mature, the results can only be trusted based on existing data and assumptions today.

As the alternative materials/components suppliers are starting to offer materials suited for recycling, this is an opportunity that needs to be further investigated in the future. The importance of design for recycling and viable recycling loops are essential for realizing these opportunities. As major parts of the safety boots market are in a business-to-business (B2B) environment, this could increase the chances of more efficient recycling schemes, as they represent direct relations between the actors involved, with more transparent flows, where decisions are made based on rational and economic grounds (Hagelüken & Meskers, 2024).

Figure 1: Safety Boot Carbon Footprint

4. Conclusions

This study highlights that significant improvements in carbon footprint are possible when LCA is applied in the early design stage, even for products with strict technical performance requirements. Combining materials to reach the demands of comfort, durability, and low weight, while continuously minimising environmental impact is key. A more holistic view considering additional environmental impact categories will allow for better-informed decision-making on (bio-based) material selection. However, obtaining high-quality and transparent environmental data on alternative textile materials from the suppliers is essential, but very challenging. Additional work, beyond LCA, is required for a circular safety boot value chain.

5. References

- [1] ISO. 2011. Personal protective equipment — Safety footwear. ISO 20345:2011.
- [2] Hagelüken C, Meskers C. 2024. Economic aspects of metal recycling. Handbook of Recycling (Second Edition) 42:627-644.

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